

Supplementary Material

Complete TRL Assessment Criteria Tables and Systematic Review Corpus

For: A Generalized AI-Powered Framework for Cross-Domain Technology Readiness Assessment

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1. Introduction

This document provides the complete assessment criteria tables referenced in the main paper. The methodology employs binary criteria organized in two categories: mandatory criteria (MUST), which must all be satisfied to validate a TRL level, and supportive criteria (SHOULD), which reinforce the evaluation but do not block validation. The overall TRL is determined by the weakest-link principle: the highest level for which all MUST criteria are satisfied. The criteria are derived from ISO 16290:2013, NASA TRL Definitions (2017), the DoD TRA Guidebook (2025), the GAO Technology Readiness Assessment Guide (2020), and the MLTRL framework (Lavin et al., 2022).

Section 2 presents the hardware/physical process criteria (Table S1). Section 3 presents the software/digital system criteria (Table S2). Section 4 presents the AI/ML criteria with additional MLTRL requirements (Table S3). Section 5 provides the environment and evidence equivalence tables. Section 6 contains the complete list of 39 primary studies from the systematic review (Table S6).

2. Hardware / Physical Process Criteria (Table S1)

TRL 1 — Basic Principles Observed

Type	Criterion	Acceptable Evidence
MUST	Underlying scientific principles are identified and documented	Technical note, internal report, paper in any journal/conference, thesis, preprint
MUST	The observed phenomenon or principle is reproducible or grounded in literature	Bibliographic reference or observation record
<i>SHOULD</i>	Potential applications of the technology are identified	Any document mentioning applicability
<i>SHOULD</i>	Publication in indexed journal (any quartile) or conference exists	Improves robustness but NOT mandatory

TRL 2 — Technology Concept Formulated

Type	Criterion	Acceptable Evidence
MUST	A documented description of the technology concept addresses its feasibility	Project proposal, formulation document, technical report, thesis in progress
MUST	The concept establishes how basic principles (TRL 1) will be used to solve an identified problem	Any document connecting principle to application
<i>SHOULD</i>	Key technical characteristics of the concept are identified (block diagram, logical model)	Diagram, schematic, or functional description
<i>SHOULD</i>	The concept has received peer review (academic or technical)	Advisor endorsement, committee review, formal feedback

TRL 3 — Experimental Proof of Concept

Type	Criterion	Acceptable Evidence
MUST	Proof-of-concept tests (simulation or experimental) validate the central principle	Simulation results, test logbook, laboratory records
MUST	Tests demonstrate the concept works under basic controlled conditions	Video, results report, simulation captures
<i>SHOULD</i>	Structured record of tests exists (logbook with dates, parameters, results)	Simple logbook, digital record, laboratory notebook
<i>SHOULD</i>	Specialized simulation tools were used (MATLAB, Proteus, SolidWorks, etc.)	Project files, screenshots with visible parameters

TRL 4 — Component Validation in Laboratory

Type	Criterion	Acceptable Evidence
MUST	Key subsystems or components are assembled and individually tested	Documented partial prototype, video, description by subsystem
MUST	Quantitative test results exist (measurements, performance metrics)	Data tables, comparative graphs, technical report
<i>SHOULD</i>	Subsystems have been partially integrated with verified interoperability	Integration report, connection diagram
<i>SHOULD</i>	Structured academic technical document of work performed exists	Report, thesis chapter, conference article

TRL 5 — Integration and Validation in Relevant Environment

Type	Criterion	Acceptable Evidence
MUST	Complete system is integrated and functional under lab conditions simulating real environment	Video of system functioning, integrated test report
MUST	Complete functional tests performed with measurement of key parameters	Report with performance metrics, results graphs
<i>SHOULD</i>	Operation manual or basic technical documentation exists	Technical manual, basic user guide
<i>SHOULD</i>	Current limitations of the system are identified and documented	Critical analysis section in technical report

TRL 6 — Demonstration in Simulated Environment

Type	Criterion	Acceptable Evidence
MUST	System demonstrated in controlled environment replicating real conditions	Video with documented environmental variables, pilot test report
MUST	Performance indicator matrix contrasted with reference values exists	Comparative metrics table, efficiency analysis
<i>SHOULD</i>	Technical feedback from experts external to development team obtained	Peer evaluation report, technical review minutes
<i>SHOULD</i>	System has documentation of test environment conditions	Documented test protocol

TRL 7 — Demonstration in Real Environment

Type	Criterion	Acceptable Evidence
MUST	Prototype has operated in real conditions (industry, field, natural environment)	Field test report with date, location, and responsible signatures
MUST	External validation from actor outside development team exists	Institutional letter from company, community, or receiving institution
MUST	Real operational metrics (not laboratory) are available	Table with field performance data
<i>SHOULD</i>	Interviews or surveys with real users were conducted	Structured questionnaire, results report

TRL 8 — Complete System Validated

Type	Criterion	Acceptable Evidence
MUST	System is fully documented (installation, operation, maintenance)	Complete technical manual
MUST	System has been tested and validated by end users or clients	Validation reports, acceptance letter from recipient
MUST	Formal validation from external agents (company, institution, regulatory body) exists	Documented validation with institutional letterhead
<i>SHOULD</i>	Measurable impact report in the application environment exists	Outcome metrics, impact evaluation report

TRL 9 — Deployment and Transfer

Type	Criterion	Acceptable Evidence
MUST	Technology is implemented in real environment with continuous, sustained use	Institutional adoption letter, use contract or agreement
MUST	Legal or formal evidence of application in external context exists	Signed contract, technology transfer agreement
<i>SHOULD</i>	Commercialization or scaling process has been initiated	Market analysis, pricing strategy, preliminary commercial agreements
<i>SHOULD</i>	Intellectual property protection has been managed	IP application, pending patent, active license

3. Software / Digital System Criteria (Table S2)

Software criteria translate each hardware concept to its computational equivalent, following the DoD TRA Guidebook 2025 (Table 2-2) and NASA parallel software definitions.

TRL 1 — Basic Principles Observed

Type	Criterion	Acceptable Evidence
MUST	Underlying computational/algorithmic principles are identified and documented	Technical note, literature review, preprint, thesis proposal
MUST	The problem domain and relevant prior work are documented	Bibliographic references, state-of-the-art analysis
<i>SHOULD</i>	Potential software applications are identified	Document mentioning use cases or applicability
<i>SHOULD</i>	Publication or formal technical document exists	Not mandatory; improves robustness

TRL 2 — Technology Concept Formulated

Type	Criterion	Acceptable Evidence
MUST	A documented software concept/architecture addresses feasibility	Architecture document, system diagram, requirements specification
MUST	The concept connects principles to a specific application	Functional requirements linking problem to solution
<i>SHOULD</i>	Key technical characteristics identified (architecture diagram, data flow)	UML, C4, or flowchart diagrams
<i>SHOULD</i>	Concept reviewed by peers or technical advisor	Formal feedback or committee review

TRL 3 — Proof of Concept (Development Environment)

Type	Criterion	Acceptable Evidence
MUST	Proof-of-concept code validates central functionality with synthetic/test data	Implemented scripts, unit tests with synthetic data, executable notebook
MUST	Core functionality demonstrated under controlled development conditions	Working code, test output, documented experiment
<i>SHOULD</i>	Structured test records exist	Test log, version control history
<i>SHOULD</i>	Development environment and dependencies documented	README, requirements.txt, Dockerfile

TRL 4 — Alpha Version: Partial Integration

Type	Criterion	Acceptable Evidence
MUST	Functional modules are partially integrated into a working prototype	Functional web prototype, connected frontend-backend, ETL pipeline
MUST	Quantitative functional test results exist	Integration test results, performance benchmarks
<i>SHOULD</i>	Repository with executable code and documentation exists	GitHub/GitLab repo with README
<i>SHOULD</i>	Academic technical document of work performed	Report, thesis chapter, conference paper

TRL 5 — Integration with Representative Data and Realistic Load

Type	Criterion	Acceptable Evidence
MUST	Integrated system tested with representative data and realistic load	Integration test report, performance benchmarks under load
MUST	End-to-end tests with performance metrics (latency, throughput, memory)	Metrics dashboard, test report with quantitative data
<i>SHOULD</i>	Complete README + API documentation	Published documentation
<i>SHOULD</i>	Known failure modes and edge cases documented	Limitations section in technical report

TRL 6 — Beta Version: Controlled User Testing

Type	Criterion	Acceptable Evidence
MUST	Beta version tested with real users in controlled environment	User testing report, usability survey results
MUST	Performance metrics contrasted with baseline or requirements	Comparative metrics table, acceptance criteria checklist
<i>SHOULD</i>	External technical feedback obtained	Peer review, expert evaluation report
<i>SHOULD</i>	Test environment conditions documented	Test protocol, environment specification

TRL 7 — Pilot Deployment in Production

Type	Criterion	Acceptable Evidence
MUST	System deployed as pilot in production with real users	Deployment log, access records, user activity data
MUST	External validation from stakeholder outside development team	Institutional acceptance letter, partner validation
MUST	Real operational metrics available (not development/test data)	Production monitoring dashboard, usage analytics
<i>SHOULD</i>	User interviews or satisfaction surveys conducted	Survey results, feedback report

TRL 8 — Pre-commercial: Documented and Externally Validated

Type	Criterion	Acceptable Evidence
MUST	System fully documented (installation, operation, API reference)	Complete technical documentation
MUST	Validated by end users or institutional clients	Validation report, acceptance letter
MUST	Formal external validation exists	Third-party code review or institutional certification
<i>SHOULD</i>	Measurable impact in application environment documented	Impact metrics, outcome evaluation

TRL 9 — Production with CI/CD and Active Support

Type	Criterion	Acceptable Evidence
MUST	System in production with continuous use and active support	SLA documentation, uptime records, support ticket system
MUST	Legal or formal evidence of external application exists	Active license (GPL/MIT/Apache/commercial), SLA contract
<i>SHOULD</i>	Commercialization or scaling initiated	Pricing strategy, user growth metrics
<i>SHOULD</i>	Intellectual property managed	License selection, IP documentation

4. AI/ML System Criteria (Table S3)

AI/ML criteria extend the software criteria with mandatory additions derived from the MLTRL framework (Lavin et al., 2022, Nature Communications). The software criteria in Section 3 apply as the base; the following additional requirements are specific to AI/ML systems.

4.1 Additional MLTRL Criteria

Criterion	Type / Level	Description
Data Readiness	MUST (TRL 3+)	Dataset is accessible, validated, and demonstrates utility (Lawrence, 2017). Prerequisite for TRL 3 in AI systems.
Pipeline Reproducibility	MUST (all levels)	Training pipeline is reproducible with fixed seed, documented dependency versions, and containerized environment (Docker/Conda).
Bias & Fairness Evaluation	MUST (TRL 7+)	Fairness analysis with documented metrics performed before TRL 7.
Switchback Provisions	MUST (all levels)	Core technology is recorded. If model, architecture, or data change radically, the modified component is re-evaluated from the corresponding level.
Model Card	SHOULD (TRL 5), MUST (TRL 6+)	Standardized document describing the model, its limitations, use cases, and known risks. Required before TRL 6.
Production Monitoring Plan	MUST (TRL 8+)	Documented monitoring plan for production (drift detection, retraining triggers). Required before TRL 8.

4.2 AI/ML-Specific Evidence Substitutions

Where hardware criteria reference physical measurements and software criteria reference code artifacts, AI/ML criteria accept the following evidence equivalents:

Hardware Evidence	Software Equivalent	AI/ML Specific Equivalent
Voltage/current/torque measurement	Performance benchmarks (latency, throughput, memory)	Model metrics: accuracy, F1, precision, recall, AUC
Simulation in Proteus/SolidWorks	Unit and integration tests	Experiments with documented validation datasets
CAD diagrams / technical plans	Architecture diagram (UML, C4, flowchart)	Model card + dataset datasheet
Material stress testing	Load/stress/security testing	Robustness evaluation (distribution shift, adversarial data)
Physical functional prototype	Repository with executable code + documentation	Trained model with reproducible, versioned pipeline
Technical operation manual	Complete README + API docs + deployment guide	Model card + inference instructions + usage policy
External validation letter	External user evaluation report / institutional letter	Third-party evaluation + documented bias/fairness audit
Technology transfer agreement	Active license (GPL/MIT/Apache/commercial) + SLA	License + documented model update policy

5. Environment Equivalences (Table S5)

Level	Hardware / Physical Process	Software / Digital / AI
TRL 3	Laboratory with real equipment or technical simulation	Development environment with synthetic or test data
TRL 4	Partial prototype of physical components	Alpha version: partially integrated functional modules
TRL 5	Complete system in controlled laboratory	Integrated system with representative data and realistic load
TRL 6	Specialized lab replicating real environment	Beta version tested with real users in controlled environment
TRL 7	Field operation: industry, community, nature	Pilot deployment in production with real users
TRL 8	Complete system approved by end users	Pre-commercial: documented, tested, validated externally
TRL 9	Technology transfer or commercialization	Production with CI/CD pipeline and active support

6. Systematic Review Corpus: 39 Primary Studies (Table S6)

Table S6 presents the complete list of 39 studies included in the systematic review, organized by application domain.

Table S6. Complete corpus of 39 primary studies included in the systematic review.

Author(s) and Year	Domain	Main Approach	Cross-d.	Auto.
Salvador-Carulla et al. (2024)	Health / Impl. Science	Scale adaptation & checklist (TRL-IS)	No	No
Salvador-Carulla et al. (2025)	Mental Health	Proof of Concept strategy (TRL-IS)	No	No
Rath et al. (2025)	Medical Innovation	Scoring system (binary card)	No	No
Huang et al. (2024)	Bionic Prosthetics	TRL scale review & adaptation	No	No
Zhang et al. (2023)	Green Transition (H ₂)	Mutation theory evaluation model	No	Yes
Milani et al. (2024)	Renewable Energy	Social acceptability meta-analysis	No	No
Petrovic & Hossain (2020)	Fuel Cells	Complementary framework (TRL+MRL)	No	No
Pereverzeva et al. (2020)	Wind Energy	Scale adaptation for energy security	No	No
Klute et al. (2024)	Heat Pumps	Maturity & economic review	No	No
Jiménez-Calvo (2024)	Photocatalysis & Energy	Scale-up & device review	No	No
Bukar & Asif (2024)	Carbon Capture	TRL review & expert evaluation	No	No
Kobos et al. (2018)	Technology Transition	Complementary framework (TRM: TRL+MRL+RRL)	Yes	Yes
Pereira et al. (2018)	Smart Grids	Policy evaluation (Delphi method)	No	No
Ramesh & Nippatlapalli (2025)	Wastewater Treatment	TRL review under circular economy	No	No
Calderon & Najafi (2025)	Water Infrastructure	Automated system (SFAHP, OPTICS, kNN)	No	Yes
White et al. (2022)	Plant Biosecurity	Excel calculator (binary checklist)	No	Yes
Sepúlveda et al. (2025)	Aquaculture (Shrimp)	TRL application (case study)	No	No
Lacueva-Pérez et al. (2018)	Manufacturing (HCI)	Taxonomy & evaluation system (subsumption)	No	Yes
Jorg et al. (2021)	Manufacturing (Robotics)	TRL scale application	No	No
Liu et al. (2024)	Logistics / Supply Chain	TRL review for Digital Twins	Yes	Yes
Fu & Zailani (2025)	Heavy Industry (Carbon)	Structural maturity analysis (PLS-SEM)	No	No
Benndorf et al. (2016)	Mining & Petroleum	Real-time optimization (closed-loop)	No	Yes
Bennett et al. (2025)	Aerospace (Landing gear)	Early-stage TRL evaluation	No	No
Karanam & Hartman (2025)	Lunar Manufacturing	Digital Twins & XR integration	No	Yes
Mahmoudi et al. (2021)	Spacecraft Life Support	Optimization algorithm (WOA) with TRL	No	Yes
Clawson (2023)	Software (Blockchain)	Scale adaptation (BRL & IRL)	No	No
Yousif et al. (2021)	Internet of Things (IoT)	Post-pandemic TRL application review	Yes	No
Simeonov (2025)	Power Electronics (Startups)	Scoring system (weighted risk index)	No	No
Osorio-Tejada et al. (2023)	Chemical Processes	ESG metrics integration with TRL	No	No
Pitaro et al. (2025)	Materials (Graphene)	Safety & sustainability framework (SSbD)	No	No
Sander-Titgemeyer et al. (2023)	Wood Sector	Iterative LCA combined with TRL	No	No
Rodríguez López et al. (2023)	SMEs (Multiple sectors)	Bibliometric & mathematical methods (SmET, BIMATEM)	Yes	Yes
Chebaeva et al. (2021)	Eco-design (R&D)	Complementary framework (SAL levels)	Yes	No
Barahmand & Eikeland (2025)	Circular Economy (Waste-to-X)	Composite cross-index (TSI & Eco-Strategic Index)	Yes	Yes
Liu et al. (2020)	Technology Transfer	Complementary framework (TRL-DRL matrix)	Yes	No
Zhong & Yang (2025)	Education (School-Enterprise)	Quantitative TRL adaptation model	No	No

Halicka (2020)	Road Infrastructure	Multi-criteria selection system (TOPSIS)	No	Yes
Bruno et al. (2020)	Public Services (e-Gov)	Multidimensional complementary framework (SRL, ORL, LRL)	No	No

Total: 38 studies. Domain-specific: 33 (84.6%). Cross-domain: 6 (15.4%). With automated component: 13 (33.3%).